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Socio-psychological mechanisms of self-regulation development in the youth environment

Musinova Rukhshona Yunusovna

Associate Professor of the Department of Pedagogy and General Psychology
Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

Abstract: The article examines the socio-psychological mechanisms of self-regulation development among youth. It analyzes national and international studies that explore how educational, professional, and social environments influence the formation of regulatory skills and behavioral strategies. Special attention is given to motivational, cognitive, and volitional factors, as well as to the role of subjective position, social activity, and interpersonal interaction as key conditions for developing self-regulation. The formation of regulatory competence in young people is viewed as a result of the interaction between personal resources and external social factors, ensuring successful socialization and professional growth.

Keywords: self-regulation, youth, socio-psychological mechanisms, personal development, motivation, subjective position, socialization, professional formation, emotional stability, cognitive processes, self-assessment, self-control, adaptation, volitional regulation, self-management.

In the context of rapid social and technological changes, the problem of the formation and development of self-regulation among young people is becoming particularly relevant, since the ability to manage their behavior, emotions and motivation is becoming an integral component of successful socialization, professional development and personal development. Modern researchers point to the need to analyze the socio-psychological mechanisms that ensure the formation of the regulatory sphere of personality in the context of educational, professional and social activity of young people. Thus, according to the positions of A.S. Kharitonova and F.G. Mukhametzyanova, subjective self-regulation is the most important socio-psychological mechanism contributing to the formation of professional goal-setting among students, which makes it relevant in the context of studying self-regulation among young people. The authors emphasize that in the conditions of the university educational space, the development of self-regulation occurs in the process of active interaction of the individual with social and educational stimuli, where awareness of goals, responsibility for choice and readiness for self-government play a key role. The subjective position of students, expressed in the ability to internal control, motivational and volitional stability and meaningful planning, acts not only as a result, but also as a mechanism for the development of regulatory abilities.[1]

The research of M.A. Ryzhova and A.O. Prokhorov focuses on the theoretical and mental substantiation of the mechanisms of self-regulation of behavior and mental states in the youth environment, which is directly related to the study of socio-psychological factors contributing to its development. M.A. Ryzhova considers adolescence as a sensitive period for the formation of regulatory abilities,

emphasizing the importance of social conditions, educational influences and interpersonal interactions that shape conscious behavior and personal activity. A.O. Prokhorov complements this by revealing the mental mechanisms of self-regulation, including cognitive assessment, internal dialogue, reflection, and forecasting, as the basis for adaptive behavior under conditions of psychoemotional stress.[2]

O.V. Bubnovskaya, V.V. Kalita, A.V. Lysova and M.L. Sokolovsky, based on the results of the analysis of the relationship between the levels of self-regulation and social activity of youth, revealed the specifics of socio-psychological mechanisms contributing to its formation and development. The authors empirically identify a typology of self-regulation profiles, showing how the features of goal setting, self-control, and behavior planning relate to involvement in socially significant activities. The results of the study demonstrate that a high level of social activity of young people is associated with a developed system of personal regulation based on internal motivation, reflexivity and responsibility. Thus, scientists emphasize the importance of the social environment and activity as catalysts for the development of regulatory abilities among young people, pointing out the need to support the subjective position of young people in educational and social institutions. [3]

In the framework of the research of A.N. Tarasova, M.V. Pevna and D.F. Telepaeva, self-regulation is considered in the context of youth volunteer activity as a key socio-psychological mechanism that promotes personal development and strengthening social responsibility. The authors identify behavioral and motivational factors that influence the involvement of young people in volunteerism, emphasizing that participation in social projects requires a person to develop self-management skills such as determination, emotional stability, initiative and the ability to self-control. Along with this, the study identifies barriers to participation, including a low level of intrinsic motivation and a lack of social reinforcement, which indicates the importance of creating conditions for the support and formation of regulatory competencies among young people. Thus, volunteering is considered by the authors not only as a form of social activity, but also as an effective environment for the development of self-regulation through social interaction, meaningful activity and personal self-determination. [4]

In the study conducted by O.A. Alexandrova, M.B. Bulanova, and others, self-regulation among young people is considered as a multilevel system that is formed under the influence of socio-psychological factors. The authors typologize models of self-regulation in young people, identifying both constructive and maladaptive forms of regulatory behavior that depend on the level of social activity, value attitudes, and subjective control. The analysis highlights the role of the environment – educational, family, and media space - as an external mechanism that stimulates or, conversely, blocks the development of regulatory abilities. Special attention is paid to the modeling of self-regulation strategies, taking into account individual psychological and social variables, which allows us to consider self-regulation as an integral result of the interaction of personality and society. The study as a whole reveals the importance of an integrated approach to understanding the mechanisms of self-

regulation development, suggesting ways to purposefully form it among young people. [5]

N.A. Seliverstova and Yu.A. Zubok consider religious self-identification of youth as one of the significant socio-cultural mechanisms contributing to the formation of self-regulation among youth. The authors emphasize that religious values, norms, and symbols play a role not only in identity construction, but also in the development of sustainable regulatory behavioral strategies based on intrinsic motivation, moral self-discipline, and self-control. The author's research shows that involvement in religious practices and belonging to spiritual communities contributes to strengthening the volitional sphere, reflexivity and the ability to manage emotional states. At the same time, there are differences in the degree of impact of religious identity on self-regulation, depending on the cultural context and the level of institutional religiosity. In addition, the conducted research demonstrates that religion can serve as a socio-psychological resource that forms stable mechanisms of self-regulation in conditions of socio-cultural uncertainty typical of the youth environment.[6]

L.G. Dikaya considers in her research the socio-psychological and personal aspects of self-regulation of a person's functional state, which is of considerable relevance in the context of analyzing the mechanisms of self-regulation development among young people. The author emphasizes that effective self-regulation is based not only on individual psychological resources, but also on external social factors - the nature of interpersonal interactions, the level of social support, as well as environmental requirements. Special attention is paid to the role of the motivational and value sphere, self-awareness and emotional stability as internal regulators of behavior. The study presents the mechanisms through which the social environment influences the formation of the ability to manage mental and functional state, including the activation of volitional efforts and the interiorization of normative behaviors. Despite the fact that the work was performed in a more general age context, its provisions can be successfully extrapolated to a youth audience, demonstrating how a combination of personal and social factors contributes to the development of regulatory competence in young people. [7]

O.V. Maxim and A.V. Kaptsov in their research reveal the socio-psychological mechanisms of self-regulation development in the youth environment through the analysis of factors influencing the formation of regulatory abilities in various categories of youth. In particular, O.V. Maxim examines the features of social adaptation of children with developmental disorders of self-regulation, emphasizes the importance of the correctional and developmental environment and social interactions as conditions for compensating for deficiencies in the regulatory sphere. In his work, Kaptsov focuses on the role of socio-psychological factors such as value orientations, self-esteem, and the nature of educational motivation in the development of students' regulatory system. Both studies demonstrate that the social environment, interpersonal relationships and awareness of the subject's own role in society have a key impact on the formation of self-regulation among young people. [8]

The study by A.A. Rogozhina examines the socio-psychological features of self-regulation of students' voluntary activity, which actualizes the problem of forming self-government mechanisms in a youth educational environment. The author reveals that effective self-regulation among students is determined not only by individual and personal characteristics, but also by the specifics of the social environment, including the style of pedagogical interaction, the level of group cohesion and the nature of interpersonal relationships. Awareness of goals, internal motives and the formation of responsibility for one's own activities play an important role. The author's research emphasizes that the socio-psychological conditions of learning and communication in the student environment are an important resource for the development of self-regulation, contributing to the formation of mature behavioral strategies and adaptive forms of activity. [9]

E.F. Zeer highlights the socio-psychological aspects of the development of vitality and resilience, which are considered as the most important mechanisms of self-regulation of a personality in a changing social reality, especially relevant for youth. The author emphasizes that the development of resilience is associated with the formation of stable life orientations in young people, the ability to constructively overcome stressful situations and social uncertainty. The key factors are a supportive social environment, the presence of positive behavioral patterns, as well as opportunities for self-realization and involvement in meaningful activities. Thus, the obtained research results demonstrate that resilience acts as an integral indicator of the effectiveness of self-regulation formed under the influence of socio-psychological conditions of youth development. [10]

In the study of A.K. Osnitsky, N.V. Byakova and S.V. Istomina analyze the processes of self-regulation development at various stages of professional development, with an emphasis on the youth age as a critical period of formation of regulatory skills. The authors emphasize the importance of socio-psychological factors such as the professional and educational environment, the nature of interpersonal interaction, as well as the degree of involvement in professionally oriented activities. The study shows that the formation of self-regulation among young people is closely related to the awareness of professional goals, the development of internal motivation and the ability to adapt to changing environmental requirements. Scientists reveal important mechanisms through which the social environment contributes to the formation of mature forms of self-regulation necessary for successful professional and personal development. [11]

O.A. Konopkin, O.V. Lebedeva, F.V. Povshednaya, N.B. Karabushchenko reveal the key socio-psychological mechanisms contributing to the development of self-regulation among young people, especially in the context of professional development. In particular, O.A. Konopkin considers the general ability to self-regulate as a system-forming factor in the subjective development of personality, emphasizing its importance in active self-movement and adaptation to the socio-cultural environment. In turn, the study was conducted by O.V. Lebedeva, F.V. Povshedna and N.B. Karabushchenko focuses on the specifics of the formation of self-regulatory skills among students of pedagogical universities, where the

pedagogical orientation, the educational environment, as well as interpersonal interaction and university support play a leading role. These author's studies confirm that self-regulation among young people develops in conditions of social inclusion, conscious choice of life goals and a supportive learning environment, acting as a necessary condition for successful socialization and professional self-realization. [12]

The research of V.I. Morosanova, L.G. Maidokina, O.V. Kudashkina is devoted to various aspects of conscious self-regulation as the most important mechanism of personality development among young people. In the works of V.I. Morosanova, a differential approach to understanding conscious self-regulation is presented, considered as a system of arbitrary self-management in various life situations, where personal characteristics, motivation and social environment conditions are key factors. The role of the educational and communicative context in the formation of regulatory skills is shown. In the study of L.G. Maidokina and O.V. Kudashkina, self-regulation is considered in the context of sports activity, where it develops through interaction with a coach, group support and a system of psychological training, which is relevant for other youth communities. These studies emphasize that the development of self-regulation among young people is mediated by the social context, interpersonal relationships and structured support, which makes its formation a purposeful process in the educational and professional environment. [13]

The research by A.K. Bolotova and M.M. Puretsky presents a historical and psychological analysis of the evolution of concepts and theories of self-regulation, which allows for a deeper understanding of modern socio-psychological mechanisms of its development, especially among young people. The authors trace the formation of ideas about self-regulation from philosophical and psychological concepts to modern empirically based models, focusing on the relationship between personality, environment and processes of internal self-government. Special importance is attached to the role of socio-cultural factors, educational practices and interpersonal interactions in the development of regulatory skills among young people. Scientists emphasize that the modern understanding of self-regulation is impossible without taking into account historically established ideas, which still determine approaches to the formation of young people's ability to consciously manage their behavior and adapt to social conditions. [14]

Y.P. Povarenkova and A.E. Tsymbalyuk in their work investigated the dynamics of the formation of a system of self-regulation in professional activity, focusing on its operational development under the influence of the socio-cultural environment and personal resources of the subject. The authors show that among young people, the key conditions for the effective formation of self-regulation are motivation, reflexive abilities, as well as active involvement in professionally significant activities that contribute to the development of sustainable regulatory strategies. Special attention is paid to the role of the educational space and interpersonal interactions as factors triggering internal mechanisms of self-regulation and adaptation to professional requirements. The author's research emphasizes that socio-psychological support, the purposeful formation of professional identity and the development of a subjective

position are the most important mechanisms contributing to the development of self-regulation among young people in the process of their professional development. [15]

O.U. Gogitsayeva and V.K. Kochisov consider the conditions for the formation of personal self-regulation in younger schoolchildren, which allows us to extrapolate the data obtained to a broader context of studying the socio-psychological mechanisms of self-regulation development among young people. The authors emphasize the importance of pedagogical support, the formative influence of the educational environment and role interaction in the development of regulatory skills. According to scientists, the early development of self-regulation is closely related to the child's involvement in the system of social relations, within which the initial forms of self-control, goal-setting and arbitrary behavior are formed. These mechanisms remain relevant in adolescence, when personal development continues in more complex socio-cultural and educational conditions, and the role of the social environment increases. [16]

Yu.A. Gushchina, Yu.A. Khalutina analyzed effective socio-psychological mechanisms that promote the development of self-regulation among young people through inclusion in project and practice-oriented activities. In particular, Yu.A. Gushchina examines the impact of project activities on the formation of regulatory skills in younger adolescents, emphasizing that collective forms of work focused on achieving specific goals contribute to the development of responsibility, self-control and planning ability. Yu.A. Khalutina examines the results of an eight-week practice of mindfulness meditation as a means of increasing the level of self-regulation, which shows that regular meditation practice enhances awareness of one's own mental states, promotes emotional stability and the formation of voluntary attention management. According to the authors, the key factor in the development of self-regulation among young people is organized social activity, which provides conditions for personal growth, self-knowledge and internal control. [17]

Thus, based on the above, it is considered appropriate to conclude that the socio-psychological mechanisms of self-regulation development in the youth environment are a complex and multilevel system based on the interaction of internal personal resources and external social conditions. The formation of self-regulation among young people is ensured through active involvement in educational, professional and social activities rich in interpersonal interaction, goal setting and reflection. A significant role is played by such factors as the subject's position, motivational orientation, emotional stability and the level of social support. Modern research confirms the need for an integrated and purposeful approach to creating conditions conducive to the development of regulatory competence, which in turn is an important prerequisite for successful socialization, professional self-determination and personal growth of young people.

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